

Web application for retrospective geomagnetic storm detection, main phase analysis and identification of solar wind influence on storm intensity

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Abstract

Geomagnetic storms are major disturbances of Earth’s magnetosphere resulting from variations in the solar wind, leading to significant changes in magnetospheric currents, plasma populations, and electromagnetic fields. This work presents a web application for retrospective detection and analysis of geomagnetic storms using hourly Dst and solar wind data from OMNIWeb. The application can be applied to the available OMNIWeb time range, from 1964 to the most recent data currently provided by the database. In the present analysis, data from 1964 up to the latest available records used in this study, ending in May 2026, were analyzed. The application detects storm events, identifies their main phases, computes solar wind derived parameters during the main phase, and examines their relationship with storm intensity. Its detection and main phase identification parameters are user-adjustable, allowing different assumptions to be tested interactively rather than imposed through a single fixed parameter set. Using the default parameter set provided by the application, 1796 storms with $\text{minDst} \leq -50$ nT were detected, including 1422 moderate storms ($-100 < \text{minDst} \leq -50$ nT), 347 intense storms ($-250 < \text{minDst} \leq -100$ nT), and 27 super-storms ($\text{minDst} \leq -250$ nT). After filtering for reliable main phase identification, 1643 storms were retained. In this filtered sample, the average main phase duration per class was 9.25 hours for moderate storms, 11.30 hours for intense storms and 13.75 hours for super-storms. After also requiring OMNIWeb solar wind data availability, 981 storms remained for examining the relationship between storm intensity and solar wind derived parameters over the main phase. The strongest correlations with $|\text{Dst}_{\text{min}}|$ were obtained for peak dawn-dusk electric field (E_{yp}) with $R = 0.842$, peak southward IMF (B_{zp}) with $R = -0.812$, and integrated electric field (E_{yi}) with $R = 0.759$. These results confirm the importance of the solar wind electric field and southward interplanetary magnetic field in geomagnetic storm development. The main contribution of the application is its adjustable detection framework, which allows users to explore how parameter choices affect storm detection, main phase identification, and solar wind association results. All outputs are downloadable for further user-defined analysis. The application is available at: <https://geomagnetic-storm-mainphase-analysis.streamlit.app/>

1 Introduction

Geomagnetic storms are major disturbances of the terrestrial magnetosphere driven by enhanced solar wind energy input. The primary physical mechanism for this energy transfer is magnetic reconnection between the interplanetary magnetic field and the Earth’s magnetic field, whose efficiency increases under sustained southward IMF conditions. Prolonged southward orientation of the interplanetary magnetic field has been empirically recognized as a primary solar wind driver

of storm development (Gonzalez and Tsurutani, 1987). However, Daglis et al. (2003) showed that the geoeffectiveness of this driver is also influenced by internal magnetospheric conditions, such as plasma sheet density, which can modify the resulting storm intensity.

Storm intensity is commonly measured by the Disturbance Storm Time index (Dst), which reflects variations in the horizontal component of the geomagnetic field measured at ground-based stations relative to quiet-time conditions. During the storm main phase, defined as the interval during which Dst decreases toward its minimum value, enhanced injection of energetic ions into the inner magnetosphere strengthens the ring current, producing the characteristic negative depression in Dst. Therefore, the minimum Dst value is commonly used as an indicator of storm intensity.

Figure 1 shows the Dst profile of an intense geomagnetic storm that occurred in January 2025, using hourly OMNIWeb values. The event provides an example of a storm with a clear main phase evolution, characterized by a sustained decrease in Dst toward a minimum value of -212 nT at 15:00 UT on 1 January 2025.

Figure 1. Dst profile of an intense geomagnetic storm that occurred in 2025, reaching its minimum Dst = -212 nT on 1 January.

In this paper, the analysis is limited to solar wind parameters as storm drivers and does not include internal magnetospheric conditions. It also does not attempt to identify the solar source or the specific interplanetary driver structures of the detected storms. However, Zhang et al. (2007) noted that the storm-driving component, which possesses a prolonged southward orientation of the interplanetary magnetic field, may be an ICME sheath, multiple interacting ICMEs, a corotating interaction region (CIR), or a combination of these structures. Such complex driving conditions may lead to highly irregular Dst profiles. Figure 2 shows some examples of more complicated Dst

profiles with multiple depressions.

Figure 2. Dst profiles of geomagnetic storms that occurred in 1991, during the solar maximum phase of Solar Cycle 22.

This paper’s main objective is to give answers to the following questions:

- When should a separate Dst depression be classified as a distinct storm?
- How is the main phase onset time determined?
- What is the relationship of storm intensity and solar wind?

It presents a web application for retrospective detection of geomagnetic storms from hourly Dst data and for identification of their main phases. The application allows users to adjust algorithm parameters, so that ambiguous events can be examined interactively rather than being classified only through one fixed set of assumptions. After storm detection and main phase identification, the application computes solar wind derived parameters during the main phase and examines their relationship with storm intensity.

2 Data set

The analysis uses hourly averaged OMNI data obtained through NASA’s OMNIWeb Data Explorer (<https://omniweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/form/dx1.html>) covering the period from 1964 up to the latest available records, ending in May 2026. The data used by the application are hourly values of the Disturbance Storm Time index (Dst), interplanetary magnetic field (IMF), the z-component of the interplanetary magnetic field (Bz), solar wind speed (V) and dawn-dusk solar wind electric field (E_y). Dst, IMF, and Bz are measured in nT, and V is measured in km/s. E_y is derived from the product $-VB_z$ and is expressed in mV/m as $E_y = -VB_z \times 10^{-3}$.

3 Algorithm and outputs

The algorithm operates in three stages. First, geomagnetic storms are detected over the time period that the user has set. Second, the detected events are filtered, and their main phases are identified. Third, derived solar wind parameters are extracted for the filtered storms with data-complete main phases.

3.1 Stage 1: Storm detection

The first stage identifies geomagnetic storms based on their Dst minima. At this stage, the program is concerned only with the minimum Dst depression of each storm and the time at which this minimum occurs.

Stage 1 algorithm parameters:

EPISODE_LEVEL defines the Dst threshold used to identify continuous disturbed intervals. A disturbed episode begins when Dst becomes equal to or lower than **EPISODE_LEVEL** and continues as long as consecutive hourly Dst values remain at or below this threshold. Thus, **EPISODE_LEVEL** acts as the initial, broad criterion for identifying magnetically disturbed periods. The default value is **−20 nT**.

STORM_LEVEL defines the Dst threshold used to identify storm-level minima within each disturbed episode. After a disturbed episode has been detected, the algorithm searches within that episode for candidate storm minima. A **candidate storm minimum** is defined as a Dst value that is equal to or lower than **STORM_LEVEL** and is also a local minimum within the surrounding time window defined by **LOCAL_MIN_RADIUS_HOURS**. The default value is **−50 nT**, which is commonly used as the threshold for identifying moderate geomagnetic storms.

LOCAL_MIN_RADIUS_HOURS defines the time window used to test whether a storm-level Dst value is a local minimum. For each Dst value that is equal to or lower than **STORM_LEVEL**, the algorithm checks whether it is the lowest Dst value within a surrounding time window of \pm **LOCAL_MIN_RADIUS_HOURS**. If it is, the point is retained as a candidate storm minimum. The default value is **3 hours**.

MINIMA_SPLIT_FACTOR defines the **minimum-splitting criterion**, which controls whether multiple candidate storm minima within the same disturbed episode are treated as separate storm events. When two candidate storm minima occur within the same episode, the algorithm examines the maximum Dst value between them, referred to here as the inter-minimum peak. The inter-minimum peak height is defined as

$$\text{peak height} = \text{inter-minimum peak} - \text{shallower minimum.} \quad (1)$$

This height is then compared with a separation threshold, defined as a fraction of the absolute depth of the deepest minimum:

$$\text{separation threshold} = -\text{deeper minimum} \times \text{MINIMA_SPLIT_FACTOR.} \quad (2)$$

If the peak height is greater than or equal to the separation threshold, the two minima are treated as separate storm events. Otherwise, they are considered part of the same storm structure, and the deeper minimum is retained as the representative minimum Dst of the storm. The default value for **MINIMA_SPLIT_FACTOR** is **0.4**.

If more than two candidate storm minima occur within the same episode, they are evaluated sequentially in chronological order. Each new candidate minimum is compared with the most recently retained minimum. If the separation criterion is satisfied, the new minimum is retained as a separate storm event. If not, the two minima are merged and only the deeper minimum is retained before the algorithm proceeds to the next candidate minimum.

STORM_LIMIT imposes a lower bound on accepted Dst minima. It allows the user to restrict the analysis to a selected storm-intensity range and to exclude events outside the desired limits.

Note: To select a specific storm-intensity range, **STORM_LEVEL** can be used as the upper threshold and **STORM_LIMIT** as the lower threshold. For example, setting **STORM_LEVEL** = -50 nT and **STORM_LIMIT** = -99 nT restricts the analysis to storms with $-99 \text{ nT} \leq Dst_{\min} \leq -50 \text{ nT}$ (moderate storms).

Outputs of Stage 1. Stage 1 produces the catalogue of all detected storms. The main table lists each detected storm together with its time of minimum Dst (t_{\min}) and the corresponding minimum Dst value (Dst_{\min}). Additional Stage 1 tables provide the characteristics of the disturbed episodes from which the storms were identified, including the episode start and end times, duration, and the number of detected storms associated with each episode. Multi-storm episodes are also reported separately, together with the corresponding storm minima identified within the same continuous Dst depression.

3.2 Stage 2: Main phase identification

In the second stage, the program identifies the main phase of each storm detected in Stage 1. Because the end of the main phase is defined by the minimum Dst time, t_{\min} , Stage 2 focuses on estimating the corresponding onset time of the main phase, t_{start} .

For each detected storm, the algorithm searches backward in time from t_{\min} . This search uses a reference Dst value, referred to as the **mark**. Once the backward search reaches a Dst value equal to or higher than the mark, the first local Dst maximum encountered is assigned as Dst_{start} , and its timestamp is assigned as t_{start} . The main phase duration is then calculated as the time difference between t_{start} and t_{\min} .

The Stage 1 storm detection parameters are not reapplied during this stage. Stage 2 uses only the storm minima and their timestamps previously identified during storm detection. Consequently, the determination of t_{start} is not constrained by the temporal limits of the original disturbed episode. Instead, the algorithm searches backward through the available Dst record until both the mark condition and the local maximum criterion are satisfied. If no valid t_{start} can be identified, the storm is excluded from the filtered storm sample. In this study, filtered storms are defined as detected storms for which the main phase can be reliably identified.

Stage 2 algorithm parameters:

STRONG_STORM_THRESHOLD separates strong storms from weaker storms for the purpose of defining the mark that will be used for main phase onset identification. The default value is -100 nT. Storms with Dst_{\min} equal to or deeper than this threshold use the fixed mark value defined by **STRONG_MARK**.

STRONG_MARK is the mark used for strong storms. The default value is -50 nT. During the backward search from t_{\min} , once Dst reaches or exceeds this value, the first local maximum

encountered is assigned as Dst_{start} , and its timestamp is assigned as t_{start} .

For weaker storms, the mark is scaled according to storm intensity:

$$\text{WEAK_MARK} = Dst_{\text{min}} \times \frac{\text{STRONG_MARK}}{\text{STRONG_STORM_THRESHOLD}}. \quad (3)$$

With the default values, this gives $\text{WEAK_MARK} = Dst_{\text{min}}/2$.

LOCAL_MAX_RADIUS_HOURS defines the time window used to identify a local Dst maximum during the backward search for the storm onset. A point is accepted as a local maximum if it has the highest Dst value within a surrounding time window of $\pm \text{LOCAL_MAX_RADIUS_HOURS}$. The default value is **3 hours**. Increasing this parameter makes the onset detection less sensitive to short-term Dst fluctuations. However, if the value is too large, an earlier local maximum may be selected when pre-storm variations are present, resulting in an overestimation of the main phase duration.

Exclusion due to previous-storm overlap

After t_{start} has been estimated, the algorithm checks whether the Dst minimum of a previously detected storm occurs between t_{start} and t_{min} of the current storm. If such a previous minimum exists, the current storm is excluded from the filtered sample. This criterion prevents the algorithm from assigning a main phase interval that extends across an earlier storm minimum. In such cases, the estimated interval no longer represents the development of a single independent storm. This exclusion helps ensure that main phase duration and the subsequent analysis of relationships with solar wind parameters are calculated only for storms with a physically meaningful onset-to-minimum interval.

Disturbance filtering

After the previous-storm exclusion has been applied, the program optionally applies a disturbance filter. This filter is applied primarily to low-intensity storm events in which the Dst evolution before Dst_{min} is irregular, containing multiple secondary dips. Such events are still geomagnetic storms, but they are separated from the filtered storm sample because their automatic t_{start} determination is less reliable. In an idealized storm evolution, Dst decreases relatively continuously from the main phase onset toward Dst_{min} . In practice, however, many storms show irregular pre-minimum Dst variations, including secondary dips before the final minimum. For low-intensity storms, these variations can make the automatic onset detection particularly ambiguous and may produce disproportionately long main phase durations, for example several tens of hours for a moderate storm with Dst_{min} near -60 nT. The disturbance filter therefore separates these ambiguous events from the filtered storm sample.

DISTURBANCE_FILTER activates or deactivates this filtering step.

DISTURB_LEVEL defines the intensity range to which the disturbance filter is applied. Only storms with Dst_{min} shallower than **DISTURB_LEVEL** are tested by the disturbance filter. With the default value of **-100 nT**, the filter is applied to moderate storms.

DISTURB_DIP_COUNT defines the minimum number of secondary Dst dips required for a storm to be classified as a disturbance. If the number of dips between t_{start} and t_{min} reaches this value, the event is excluded from the filtered storm sample and added to the disturbance category. The default value is **2**.

DISTURB_DIP_RADIUS_HOURS defines the time window used to identify secondary Dst dips during disturbance filtering. Between t_{start} and t_{min} , the algorithm checks whether each Dst

value is the lowest value within a surrounding time window of \pm DISTURB_DIP_RADIUS_HOURS. If it is, the point is counted as a secondary Dst dip. The default value is **3 hours**. A larger radius makes the filter less sensitive to short-term Dst fluctuations, reducing the number of detected secondary dips and making storms less likely to be classified as disturbances.

Outputs of Stage 2. Stage 2 produces the catalogue of filtered storms. For each retained storm, the output table includes the Stage 1 storm information, such as t_{\min} and Dst_{\min} , together with the estimated main phase onset time, t_{start} , the corresponding Dst_{start} , and the main phase duration. Additional Stage 2 tables list storms excluded because of previous-storm overlap, as well as storms classified as disturbances, including their automatically estimated but unreliable t_{start} values and main phase durations.

3.3 Stage 3: Solar wind derived parameter computation

In Stage 3, the program uses the OMNIWeb solar wind data within the main phase intervals identified after Stage 2 filtering to compute the corresponding solar wind derived parameters for each storm. Before computing the final parameters, the program checks the OMNIWeb solar wind data for missing values during the main phase of each storm. If a single value is missing for a given parameter, it is replaced by linear interpolation using the neighboring valid values. Storms containing multiple consecutive missing values during their main phase are rejected from the final data-complete sample. This step ensures that the derived solar wind parameters are calculated only for storms with sufficiently complete input data.

For each data-complete storm, the derived solar wind parameters are computed over the main phase and include the IMF peak (IMFp), Bz peak (Bzp), solar wind speed peak (Vp), Ey peak (Eyp), and integrated Ey (Eyi). The Bz peak is defined as the most negative Bz value during the main phase, whereas the other peak quantities correspond to the maximum values reached during the same interval.

Outputs of Stage 3. Stage 3 produces the final catalogue of the data-complete storms. The main output table lists each Stage 2 storm that was not rejected due to incomplete solar wind data. In addition to the storm quantities already determined in the previous stages, namely t_{\min} , Dst_{\min} , t_{start} , Dst_{start} , and main phase duration, each storm is now listed together with its derived solar wind parameters. Additional Stage 3 output tables provide complementary information for the data-complete storms, including the time delays between Bzp, Eyp, and Dst_{\min} , as well as the timestamps at which all peak parameters occur. The program also produces a list of storms for which a single missing value was replaced by interpolation, together with the replaced value, and a list of rejected storms, including the failed parameters and the number of missing values.

3.4 Additional outputs

Additional outputs include Pearson correlation coefficients between the absolute storm intensity, $|Dst_{\min}|$, and the solar wind derived parameters of the data-complete storms, as well as scatter plots of $|Dst_{\min}|$ vs. IMFp, Bzp, Vp, Eyp, Eyi, and main phase duration. A second set of Pearson correlation tables is also produced using parameter-specific data-complete samples. In this case, a storm may be included in the correlation analysis for one parameter, such as Bz, even if it contains missing values in another parameter, such as V or Ey. As a result, the sample size may differ

between parameters and is generally larger than the fully data-complete sample, providing a less restrictive basis for the correlation analysis, especially when selected storm subsets are small. For Ey-related parameters, namely Eyp and Eyi, the available sample is constrained by both Bz and V, since Ey is derived from their product. Therefore, missing values in either Bz or V also led to missing Ey values, making the Eyp and Eyi samples the same as the full data-complete sample.

Finally, the output tables from all stages are exported as downloadable CSV files.

3.5 Examples

Example 1. In this example, the October 2003 superstorm sequence is used to illustrate how the algorithm operates across all three stages. Figure 3 shows the hourly Dst variation from 28 October to 2 November 2003 in the upper panel and how the algorithm would evaluate this event in the lower panel. Within the main disturbed episode, defined by EPISODE_LEVEL = -20 nT and shown by the red dashed line, the algorithm searches for candidate storm minima. These are local Dst minima within a ± 3 h window, set by LOCAL_MIN_RADIUS_HOURS = 3 h, with values lower than STORM_LEVEL = -50 nT. Five candidate minima are identified: -151 nT, -353 nT, -383 nT, -88 nT, and -69 nT, shown in red circles.

The minimum-splitting criterion was then applied sequentially to determine whether consecutive candidate minima should be retained as separate storm events or merged into the same storm structure. The first candidate minimum, Dst = -151 nT, was compared with the following deeper minimum, Dst = -353 nT. The inter-minimum peak between them was -79 nT. Therefore,

$$\text{peak height} = -79 - (-151) = 72 \text{ nT}. \quad (4)$$

This peak height is represented by the smaller green arrow in the figure. The corresponding separation threshold was

$$\text{separation threshold} = -(-353) \times 0.4 = 141.2 \text{ nT}. \quad (5)$$

Since the peak height was smaller than the separation threshold, the two minima were assigned to the same storm structure, and the deeper Dst = -353 nT minimum was retained.

The retained Dst = -353 nT minimum was then compared with the next candidate minimum, Dst = -383 nT. The inter-minimum peak between them was -97 nT. Therefore,

$$\text{peak height} = -97 - (-353) = 256 \text{ nT}. \quad (6)$$

This peak height is represented by the larger green arrow. The corresponding separation threshold was

$$\text{separation threshold} = -(-383) \times 0.4 = 153.2 \text{ nT}. \quad (7)$$

In this case, the peak height exceeded the separation threshold. Therefore, the Dst = -383 nT minimum was retained as a separate storm event.

The two later candidate minima, Dst = -88 nT and Dst = -69 nT, were then compared sequentially with the currently retained Dst = -383 nT minimum. In both cases, the inter-minimum peak was insufficient to satisfy the minimum-splitting criterion, so these later minima were not retained as separate storm events.

As a result, Stage 1 detected two storms within the same disturbed episode: one with $Dst_{\min} = -353$ nT at 30 October 2003, 00:00 UTC, and another with $Dst_{\min} = -383$ nT at 30 October 2003, 22:00 UTC.

Stage 2 was then applied to the two detected storms in order to identify their onset times and assess whether their main phase intervals were suitable for further analysis. Both detected storms had Dst_{\min} values deeper than $STRONG_STORM_THRESHOLD = -100$ nT. Therefore, for both storms, the strong-storm Dst reference mark $STRONG_MARK = -50$ nT was used, shown by the blue dashed line. During the backward search from each storm minimum, after crossing this mark, the algorithm selected the first local Dst maximum within a ± 3 h window, set by $LOCAL_MAX_RADIUS_HOURS = 3$ h.

For the first storm, with $Dst_{\min} = -353$ nT, the algorithm identified Dst_{start} at 29 October 2003 06:00 UTC, when $Dst = -10$ nT, shown in the blue circle. The resulting main phase duration was 18 hours, and the storm was retained in the filtered storm sample.

For the second storm, with $Dst_{\min} = -383$ nT, the backward search led to the same Dst_{start} point, so the Dst_{\min} of the first storm occurred between this Dst_{start} time and the Dst_{\min} of the second storm. Therefore, the estimated main phase of the second storm overlapped the previous storm and was not considered independent. As a result, the second storm was excluded from the filtered storm sample.

In Stage 3, the storm retained after Stage 2 was tested for OMNI data completeness over its main phase, from 29 October 2003 at 06:00 UTC to 30 October 2003 at 00:00 UTC. Although the Dst main phase was well defined, the V and Ey parameters contained consecutive missing values throughout the interval. Because the algorithm only replaces isolated internal missing values, this storm was rejected from the final data-complete sample.

Thus, Stage 1 detected two storm events within the disturbed episode, with $Dst_{\min} = -353$ nT and $Dst_{\min} = -383$ nT. Stage 2 retained only the first storm in the filtered storm sample, while Stage 3 rejected it from the final data-complete sample.

Figure 3. Hourly Dst variation from 28 October to 2 November 2003. The upper panel shows the Dst profile during the selected interval. The lower panel illustrates how the algorithm evaluates the event. Red circles show the local Dst minima deeper than -50 nT. The green arrows indicate the inter-minimum peak heights. The blue circle shows the main phase onset of the first super-storm event with $Dst_{\min} = -353$ nT. The red dashed line denotes the episode level, and the blue dashed line denotes the strong-storm Dst reference mark used for main phase onset identification.

Example 2. In this example, the importance of the reference mark in the main phase onset identification procedure is demonstrated. Figure 4 shows the hourly Dst variation from 28 March to 2 April 1990 in the upper panel and how the algorithm would evaluate this event with focus on the Stage 2 strong-storm Dst reference mark. Within the detected episode, defined by $\text{EPISODE_LEVEL} = -20$ nT and shown by the red dashed line, the algorithm searches for local Dst minima using a ± 3 h window, set by $\text{LOCAL_MIN_RADIUS_HOURS} = 3$ h. The deepest minimum occurs on 30 March 1990 at 11:00 UTC, where Dst reaches -187 nT, shown in the red square. Although additional local minima deeper than $\text{STORM_LEVEL} = -50$ nT occur earlier within the same episode, they are not classified as separate storm events because they do not satisfy the minimum-splitting criterion relative to the dominant -187 nT minimum.

As a result, Stage 1 detected one storm during this time period with $Dst_{\min} = -187$ nT at 30 March 1990, 11:00 UTC.

In Stage 2, the main phase onset is determined for the detected storm. Since the storm is stronger than the $\text{STRONG_STORM_THRESHOLD} = -100$ nT, the strong-storm Dst reference mark, $\text{STRONG_MARK} = -50$ nT, is used, shown by the blue dashed line. Searching backward from the storm minimum, the algorithm identifies the first point at which Dst crosses this mark. This occurs on 30 March 1990 at 07:00 UTC, where $Dst = -41$ nT. Since this point is also a local maximum within a ± 3 h window, set by $\text{LOCAL_MIN_RADIUS_HOURS} = 3$ h, it is accepted as the main phase onset, shown in the blue circle.

Thus, the storm main phase extends from 30 March 1990 at 07:00 UTC to 30 March 1990 at 11:00 UTC, with a total duration of 4 h.

This example illustrates the importance of the strong-storm Dst reference mark, STRONG_MARK . A disturbed interval is present before the rapid storm development. If the backward search had instead relied on a fixed quiet-time threshold, the inferred onset would have shifted to a much earlier part of the disturbed interval, resulting in an overestimated main phase duration that would not represent the actual storm build-up.

Figure 4. Hourly Dst variation from 28 March to 2 April 1990. The upper panel shows the Dst profile during the selected interval. The lower panel highlights the detected storm minimum, shown in the red square, and the main phase onset, shown in the blue circle. The red dashed line denotes the episode level and the blue dashed line denotes the strong-storm Dst reference mark used for main phase onset identification.

Example 3. This example illustrates the operation of the weak-storm Dst reference mark and the disturbance filter. Figure 5 shows the hourly Dst variation from 18 to 25 December 2006 in the upper panel and how the algorithm would evaluate this event in the lower panel. Within the main detected episode, defined by $EPISODE_LEVEL = -20$ nT and shown by the red dashed line, the algorithm finds two local Dst minima deeper than $STORM_LEVEL = -50$ nT: one on 20 December 2006 at 21:00 UTC, where $Dst = -51$ nT, and another on 22 December 2006 at 10:00 UTC, where $Dst = -51$ nT.

The minimum-splitting criterion is then applied to determine whether these two candidate minima should be treated as separate storm events. The inter-minimum peak between them occurs on 22 December 2006 at 02:00 UTC, where $Dst = -30$ nT. Therefore, the peak height is

$$\text{peak height} = -30 - (-51) = 21 \text{ nT}. \quad (8)$$

This peak height is represented by the green arrow. The corresponding separation threshold was

$$\text{separation threshold} = -(-51) \times 0.4 = 20.4 \text{ nT}. \quad (9)$$

Since the peak height exceeds the separation threshold, Stage 1 classifies the two minima as separate storm events.

In Stage 2, both detected storms are treated as weak storms because their Dst minima are not deeper than $STRONG_STORM_THRESHOLD = -100$ nT. Therefore, the Dst reference mark is scaled from the storm intensity, giving a value of

$$\mathbf{WEAK_MARK} = Dst_{\min} \times \frac{STRONG_MARK}{STRONG_STORM_THRESHOLD} = -51 \times \frac{-50}{-100} = -25.5 \text{ nT} \quad (10)$$

for both storms, shown by the blue dashed line. For the first storm, the backward search identifies the main phase onset on 18 December 2006 at 20:00 UTC, where $Dst = -12$ nT, shown in the blue circle. However, the interval between this onset and the storm minimum contains multiple secondary Dst dips, indicated by red crosses, defined as being the lowest value within the surrounding $\pm DISTURB_DIP_RADIUS_HOURS = 3$ h window. Since the number of Dst dips is at least $DISTURB_DIP_COUNT = 2$, the event is classified as a disturbance and is rejected from the filtered storm sample. For the second storm, the backward search identified the same main phase onset time. As a result, the Dst_{\min} of the first detected storm occurred between this onset time and the Dst_{\min} time of the second storm. Therefore, the estimated main phase interval of the second storm overlapped the previous storm and was not considered independent. Consequently, the second storm was also excluded from the filtered storm sample.

Thus, although Stage 1 detects two storms with $Dst_{\min} = -51$ nT, Stage 2 rejects both. Consequently, no storm from this interval is retained in the filtered storm sample.

Figure 5. Hourly Dst variation from 18 to 25 December 2006. The upper panel shows the Dst profile during the selected interval. The lower panel illustrates how the algorithm evaluates the event. Red circles show the local Dst minima deeper than -50 nT. The green arrow indicates the inter-minimum peak height. The blue circle shows the identified main phase onset of the first weak storm of $Dst_{\min} = -51$ nT before its rejection by the disturbance filter. The red dashed line denotes the episode level and the blue dashed line denotes the weak-storm Dst reference mark used for main phase onset identification.

4 Results

The results presented in this work are based on data covering the period from 1964 to May 2026 and were obtained using the default algorithm parameters of the application. The total storms detected with $\text{minDst} \leq -50$ nT were **1796**. Table 1 shows the detected storm count per class (moderate storms: $-100 < \text{minDst} \leq -50$ nT, intense storms: $-250 < \text{minDst} \leq -100$ nT, super-storms: $\text{minDst} \leq -250$ nT).

Table 1. Detected storm count per class.

Class	Detected storms
Moderate ($-100 < \text{minDst} \leq -50$)	1422
Intense ($-250 < \text{minDst} \leq -100$)	347
Super-storm ($\text{minDst} \leq -250$)	27

After filtering for reliable main phase identification, **1643** storms were retained, with an average main phase duration of **9.73 ± 0.13 hours**. Table 2 shows the filtered storm count and the average main phase duration per class.

Table 2. Filtered storm count and average main phase duration per class.

Class	Filtered storms	Avg. Mp duration (h)
Moderate	1284	9.25 ± 0.13
Intense	335	11.30 ± 0.34
Super-storm	24	13.75 ± 1.52

After also requiring OMNIWeb solar wind data availability, **981** storms were available for examining the relationship between storm intensity and solar wind derived parameters during the main phase. Table 3 shows the correlations between $|\text{min. } Dst|$ and solar wind derived parameters, main phase duration for all data-complete storms. Among these 981 storms, 788 were moderate, 183 were intense and 10 were super-storms. The average time delay of the minimum Dst from Eyp and Bzp was 3.81 ± 0.10 h and 3.83 ± 0.10 h respectively. Figure 7 shows scatter plots of $|\text{min. } Dst|$ against the parameters listed in Table 3.

Table 3. R and p-values of $|\text{min. } Dst|$ and solar wind derived parameters, main phase duration ($N = 981$, $|\text{min. } Dst| \geq 50$).

Derived parameter	R	p-value
IMFp	0.726	3.41×10^{-161}
Bzp	-0.812	1.70×10^{-231}
Eyp	0.842	2.95×10^{-264}
Eyi	0.759	7.46×10^{-185}
Vp	0.291	1.56×10^{-20}
Mp duration	0.116	2.69×10^{-4}

By setting **STORM_LEVEL** to **-200 nT**, all storms with $|\text{min. } Dst| \geq 200$ nT were detected over the same time period (1964 to May 2026). The total detected were 59, retained after main

phase filtering were 55 and the final data-complete count was 31. Table 4 shows the correlations between $|\min. Dst|$ and solar wind derived parameters, main phase duration for the data-complete storms with $|\min. Dst| \geq 200$ nT.

Table 4. R and p-values of $|\min. Dst|$ and solar wind derived parameters, main phase duration ($N = 31$, $|\min. Dst| \geq 200$).

Derived parameter	R	p-value
IMFp	0.586	5.34×10^{-4}
Bzp	-0.761	6.63×10^{-7}
Eyp	0.584	5.61×10^{-4}
Eyi	0.642	9.77×10^{-5}
Vp	0.049	7.93×10^{-1}
Mp duration	-0.079	6.74×10^{-1}

Since this sample is relatively small, data completeness was also examined separately for each solar wind parameter. The data-complete storm set remained unchanged for Ey, while the corresponding set for Bz included 4 additional storms. These 4 cases had available Bz values but missing solar wind speed (V) values, so Ey was also unavailable, since it is derived from the product of V and Bz. Using the parameter-specific data-complete sample for Bz, the Bzp sample increased to $N = 35$, yielding a correlation coefficient of $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{0.668}$ with $|\min. Dst|$.

5 Web application screenshots

storm_id	Dst_min	t_min	Dst_start	t_start	Mp duration	IMFp	Bzp	Vp	Eyp	Eyi
1331	-300	2000-07-16 01:00	7	2000-07-15 16:00	9	51.60	-45.30	1107	47.11	133.53
1534	-247	2005-05-15 09:00	52	2005-05-15 04:00	5	54.80	-36.50	928	33.87	68.38
1492	-422	2003-11-20 21:00	-17	2003-11-20 09:00	12	55.80	-50.90	703	31.25	198.57
1365	-387	2001-03-31 09:00	26	2001-03-31 04:00	5	46.90	-44.70	716	30.62	90.78
1514	-374	2004-11-08 07:00	61	2004-11-07 20:00	11	47.80	-44.90	728	29.50	215.66
1897	-333	2024-10-11 02:00	47	2024-10-10 16:00	10	43.70	-42.20	740	28.95	136.02
1543	-184	2005-08-24 12:00	29	2005-08-24 07:00	5	55.40	-42.90	635	27.24	44.40
1880	-406	2024-05-11 03:00	66	2024-05-10 18:00	9	68.90	-35.30	742	26.19	136.19
1941	-236	2026-01-20 17:00	47	2026-01-19 20:00	21	65.40	-21.80	1125	24.44	159.57

Figure 6. Application screenshot of the data-complete storm catalogue, sorted from the strongest to the weakest peak dawn-dusk solar wind electric field (Eyp). Only the first nine storms are visible in this view.

Figure 7. Scatter plots of $|Dst_{min}|$ and derived parameters: IMFp, Bzp, Eyp, Eyi, Vp, main phase duration. The solid lines indicate least-squares linear fits of $|Dst_{min}|$ vs. IMFp, Bzp, Eyp and Eyi.

6 Discussion

The main contribution of the present work lies in the development of a flexible and reproducible analysis framework. Whereas previous geomagnetic storm studies often rely on fixed thresholds or predefined event lists, the proposed application provides an adjustable framework in which users can modify the parameters controlling storm detection and main phase identification and examine how these choices affect the resulting outputs. In this sense, the application also serves as an organizational tool, as it collects and structures information on geomagnetic storms and their main phases. All generated outputs are downloadable and can be used for further user-defined analysis.

The results confirm the expected importance of southward IMF orientation and the solar wind electric field in geomagnetic storm development. This is consistent with the [Burton et al. \(1975\)](#) Dst formulation, in which the ring current injection rate is linearly proportional to the dawn-dusk component of the interplanetary electric field. The strongest associations with $|Dst_{\min}|$ are obtained for Ey, Bz, and integrated Ey. This agrees with the physical interpretation that sustained southward IMF and enhanced dawn-dusk electric field are efficient drivers of storm intensification. More specifically, the correlation analysis of derived solar wind parameters vs. $|\min. Dst|$ for the full data-complete sample of 981 storms with $|\min. Dst| \geq 50$ nT showed that the best predictor of storm intensity is Eyp ($R = 0.842$), followed by Bzp ($R = -0.812$) and then by Eyi ($R = 0.759$). This suggests that, when all three storm classes are included in the analysis (moderate, intense, super-storm), the peak value of the dawn-dusk solar wind electric field during the main phase shows the strongest association with storm intensity. It is important to note that the sample is dominated by moderate storms ($-100 < \min Dst \leq -50$), which account for about 80% of all events. Although IMFp also exhibits a strong correlation with storm intensity ($R = 0.726$), it is weaker than the correlation obtained for Bzp ($R = -0.812$). This shows that the southward component of the interplanetary magnetic field is more relevant than the total IMF magnitude, consistent with the physical role of southward Bz in enhancing magnetic reconnection between the interplanetary magnetic field and the Earth's magnetic field.

These findings are consistent with previous studies. [Gonzalez and Echer \(2005\)](#) analyzed 64 storms with $|\min. Dst| \geq 85$ nT during 1997–2002 and reported strong correlations for Bzp ($R = -0.82$) and Eyp ($R = 0.87$), while the correlation for Eyi, integrated up to the time of Bzp, was weaker ($R = 0.53$). [Balachandran et al. \(2021\)](#) analyzed 130 storms with $|\min. Dst| > 100$ nT during 1967–2018 and found correlations of $R = -0.73$ for Bzp and $R = 0.56$ ($N=124$) for Eyi. [Echer et al. \(2008\)](#) analyzed 90 storms with $|\min. Dst| \geq 100$ nT during 1996–2006 and also reported strong correlations for Bzp ($R = -0.80$) and Eyp ($R = 0.84$).

For stronger storms ($|\min. Dst| \geq 200$ nT), the present analysis gives a stronger correlation for Eyi ($R = 0.642$) than for Eyp ($R = 0.584$). This suggests that, for stronger storms, peak values alone may not capture storm intensity as effectively as sustained solar wind driving. This is physically reasonable because stronger storms require a substantial build-up of the ring current during the main phase. In the [Burton et al. \(1975\)](#) Dst formulation, the ring current injection rate is linearly proportional to the dawn-dusk interplanetary electric field. Thus, a sustained Ey driver, represented by the time-integrated Ey parameter, can show a stronger relationship with storm intensity than the peak Ey value alone. This result is consistent with [Watari et al. \(2023\)](#), who analyzed 18 intense geomagnetic storms during 1996–2021 with $|\min. Dst| > 200$ nT and found a stronger correlation for Eyi ($R = 0.838$) than for Eyp ($R = 0.586$). Future work will include applying the present application to the specific storm sample used by [Watari et al. \(2023\)](#), in order to enable a more direct and detailed comparison of the results.

Several limitations remain. The main phase onset is based on an operational estimate and may remain ambiguous for highly complex storms. In addition, missing OMNI values substantially reduce the final storm sample used in the solar wind analysis: from 1643 filtered storms, only 981 remain data-complete. This mainly affects older storms, where missing values are more frequent in the available measurements.

Future work could also include comparison with established storm catalogs, classification by solar wind driver type, analysis based on solar cycle and identification of initial and recovery phase to get the full profile of the storms.

7 Conclusions

A web application was developed for retrospective detection and analysis of geomagnetic storms using hourly Dst and OMNIWeb solar wind data. The application detects past storms, identifies their main phases, computes solar wind derived parameters during the main phase, and evaluates their association with storm intensity.

Using the selected default parameters, the application detected 1796 storms from 1964 to May 2026, consisting of 1422 moderate storms, 347 intense storms, and 27 super-storms. After filtering for reliable main phase identification, 1643 storms were retained. In this filtered sample, the average main phase duration per class was 9.25 hours for moderate storms, 11.30 hours for intense storms and 13.75 hours for super-storms. After applying the additional requirement of complete OMNIWeb solar wind data availability, the sample was reduced to 981 storms, which were then used to examine the relationship between storm intensity and solar wind derived parameters over the main phase.

The strongest correlations with $|\min. Dst|$ were found for Ey peak ($R = 0.842$), Bz peak ($R = -0.812$), and integrated Ey ($R = 0.759$). These results support the importance of the solar wind electric field and southward IMF in storm intensification. In contrast, solar wind speed and main phase duration exhibited weak correlations with storm intensity ($R = 0.291$ and $R = 0.116$, respectively).

Overall, the application provides a flexible and reproducible framework for geomagnetic storm detection, main phase identification, and solar wind association analysis. By allowing the algorithm parameters to be adjusted and by exporting all results as CSV files, the tool supports further user-defined analysis.

8 App availability

The web application is available at: <https://geomagnetic-storm-mainphase-analysis.streamlit.app/>

Note: An earlier version of this work was presented as a poster at the 16th Quadrennial Solar-Terrestrial Physics Symposium, 2026.

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